

Potentiometric Studies on some Binary and Mixed Ligand Complexes of Dioxouranium(II)

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Manuscript received 2 February 1987, revised 27 July 1987, accepted 22 August 1987

Stability constants of binary complexes of UO_2^{II} with nitrilotriacetic, suberic and azelaic acids as ligands and of mixed ligand complexes of UO_2^{II} with nitrilotriacetic acid as a primary ligand and suberic and azelaic acids as secondary ligands at 5, 25 and 45° and in different ratios of water to non-aqueous solvents and at different ionic strengths have been determined. The effect of dielectric constant and ionic strength on the values of stability constants have been discussed on the basis of steric factors and structural characteristics of the complexes formed.

IN ternary complexes uranium is hexacoordinated¹⁻³ while in quaternary complexes using bidentate ligands the coordination number exhibited is eight^{4,5}. Recently from our laboratory, reports on mixed ligand complexes of UO_2^{II} using aminopolycarboxylic acids as primary ligands and bidentate secondary ligands have appeared. When tridentate iminodiacetic acid is used as a primary ligand⁶, the coordination number exhibited is seven, while using tetradentate nitrilotriacetic acid⁷ the coordination number is eight. In this paper we report the complexation of UO_2^{II} with azelaic acid and suberic acid in the binary systems and UO_2^{II} /nitrilotriacetic acid/azelaic acid or suberic acid in ternary system. UO_2^{II} /nitrilotriacetic acid system is repeated under the experimental conditions.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Uranyl nitrate solution (0.02 M) was prepared in nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis and the uranium content was estimated gravimetrically⁸. The ligand solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and estimated potentiometrically. Methanol and ethanol were purified by standard methods⁹. All experiments were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. A ECIL expanded scale pH meter (accuracy ± 0.02 pH units) with glass-calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. Temperature was maintained constant with an accuracy of $\pm 0.02^\circ$ by dipping the reaction vessel in Ultracryostat MK-70.

The experimental procedure for binary system was similar to the one described earlier¹⁰ maintaining metal-ligand ratio to 1:5, except that instead of perchloric acid, nitric acid was used in the present case. For mixed ligand system, the procedure was similar to the one described earlier⁶.

Irving-Rossotti's pH titration technique¹¹ as modified by Bhattacharya and coworkers were used

for calculating stability constants. Titrations were carried out at 5, 25 and 45° and at $\mu=0.2$ M KNO_3 . For studying the effect of dielectric constant of the medium, the titrations were performed in methanol-water and ethanol-water media containing 10, 20, 30 and 40% (v/v) methanol or ethanol at 25° and $\mu=0.2$ M. The effect of change in ionic strength ($\mu=0.05, 0.1, 0.15$ and 0.2 M) at 25° was also studied for the UO_2^{II} -NTA-SA and UO_2^{II} -NTA-AA systems.

Results and Discussion

The binary UO_2^{II} -NTA complex was formed at pH ≈ 2.0 and the $\bar{n}$ reached a value of unity at pH ≈ 3.0 . The $\bar{n}$ value remained unaltered upto pH ≈ 5.6 but increased at pH ≈ 5.6 due to hydrolysis of the complex. The 1:1 binary UO_2^{II} -SA complex was formed at pH $\approx 2.8-4.0$, and at pH ≈ 3.9 the complex starts hydrolysing. The binary UO_2^{II} -AA complex was formed at pH $\approx 3.0-3.8$, and at pH ≈ 3.8 the complex starts hydrolysing.

In ternary complex, the secondary ligand did not participate in the reaction upto pH ≈ 3.2 . At pH ≈ 3.2 the secondary ligand starts attaching itself to the primary $[UO_2^{II}-NTA]^-$ complex to form the ternary $[UO_2^{II}-NTA-AA/SA]^-$ complex. The hydrolysis of primary complex was suppressed due to the attachment of secondary ligand, the ternary complex hydrolysed beyond pH ≈ 5.6 . The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants at three temperatures are incorporated in Table 1. The observed order of stabilities of binary and ternary complexes are NTA > AA > SA and AA > SA, respectively. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants are considerably influenced by the dielectric constant of the medium because of the fact that at least one of the constituents are either charged or polar. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants increase with increase in percentage of non-aqueous

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TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS AT 25° AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AND AT 5° AND 45° AT FIXED IONIC STRENGTH $\mu=0.2 M$ (KNO₃) IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Temp.	5°	0.05	0.1	25°	0.2	0.0	45°
Ionic strength (μ)	0.2			0.15			0.2
System	Constant						
H-SA	$\log K_1^H$	4.96	4.96	4.90	4.85	4.76	4.70
	$\log K_2^H$	4.10	4.16	4.13	4.04	4.00	3.98
H-AA	$\log K_1^H$	5.40	5.64	5.50	5.40	5.30	5.25
	$\log K_2^H$	4.00	4.34	4.12	4.01	3.92	3.82
H-NTA	$\log K_1^H$	9.75	—	—	—	9.60	9.55
	$\log K_2^H$	2.55	—	—	—	2.45	2.40
	$\log K_3^H$	1.95	—	—	—	1.80	1.85
UO ₂ ^{II} -SA	$\log K_{MA}^M$	5.77	5.95	5.81	5.72	5.61	5.43
UO ₂ ^{II} -AA	$\log K_{MA}^M$	5.89	6.00	5.88	5.77	5.67	5.44
UO ₂ ^{II} -NTA	$\log K_{MA}^M$	9.94	—	—	—	9.86	9.77
UO ₂ ^{II} -NTA-SA	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.53	3.60	3.45	3.38	3.25	3.06
UO ₂ ^{II} -NTA-AA	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.94	4.14	4.02	3.97	3.84	3.78

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN AQUEOUS ORGANIC MIXTURES
Temp. = 25°, $\mu=0.2 M$

System	Constant*	Percentage of methanol (ethanol)				
		0	10	20	30	40
H-SA	$\log K_1^H$	4.76 (4.76)	5.14 (5.18)	5.42 (5.36)	5.80 (5.76)	5.96 (6.10)
	$\log K_2^H$	4.00 (4.00)	4.24 (4.24)	4.46 (4.54)	4.68 (4.80)	4.92 (5.10)
H-AA	$\log K_1^H$	5.30 (5.30)	5.50 (5.62)	5.58 (5.74)	5.66 (5.92)	5.75 (6.08)
	$\log K_2^H$	3.92 (3.92)	4.12 (4.20)	4.16 (4.48)	4.20 (4.86)	4.27 (5.20)
H-NTA	$\log K_1^H$	9.60 (9.60)	9.80 (9.80)	9.94 (9.96)	10.10 (10.18)	10.28 (10.88)
	$\log K_2^H$	2.45 (2.45)	2.64 (2.70)	2.68 (2.74)	2.74 (2.80)	2.86 (2.90)
	$\log K_3^H$	1.80 (1.80)	2.00 (2.01)	2.04 (2.07)	2.10 (2.14)	2.16 (2.22)
[UO ₂ ^{II} -SA]	$\log K_{MA}^M$	5.61 (5.61)	5.76 (5.82)	5.92 (5.98)	6.16 (6.19)	6.42 (6.35)
[UO ₂ ^{II} -AA]	$\log K_{MA}^M$	5.67 (5.67)	5.84 (5.76)	6.04 (6.10)	6.28 (6.48)	6.60 (6.92)
[UO ₂ ^{II} -NTA]	$\log K_{MA}^M$	9.86 (9.86)	10.00 (10.20)	10.30 (10.42)	10.68 (10.70)	11.08 (11.06)
[UO ₂ ^{II} -NTA-SA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.25 (3.25)	3.30 (3.42)	3.46 (3.64)	3.68 (3.94)	3.92 (4.28)
[UO ₂ ^{II} -NTA-AA]	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.84 (3.84)	3.88 (3.92)	4.00 (4.18)	4.16 (4.44)	4.34 (4.78)

* Error limit: $pK^H = \pm 0.03 - 0.05$, $\log K = \pm 0.06 - 0.08$.

solvents (Table 2). This observation is in agreement with the earlier observations. The plots of $\log K$ vs $1/D$ (D , dielectric constant) were non-linear while that of $\log K$ vs mole fraction were linear over the

entire range for all the systems. Hence, it may be concluded that the ion-ion interaction involving the metal ion and anionic oxygen donor of the ligand increases to a greater extent as compared to the ion-

dipole interaction between the metal and the solvent molecules as the dipole moment of the medium decreases¹¹.

$\log K^H$ and $\log K$ values were found to decrease with the increase in ionic strength of the medium. The thermodynamic constants were evaluated from the pK and $\log K$ values at different ionic strength (Table 1).

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